

Artificial Intelligence in Engineering Learning: How Do Engineering Students Use It?

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Abstract

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) is capable of creating texts, music, images, and programming code. These new pieces of information are generated based on learned patterns. Since then, several companies working in AI development have introduced various products to meet the demands of different fields, such as content creation, entertainment, and education. In the educational field, there has been extensive discussion about its use, addressing both its positive and negative aspects. This study aims to present the use of the NotebookLM AI, developed by Google Labs, as a pedagogical tool in engineering courses at the Fluminense Federal University in Brazil. The methodology combines active learning strategies with AI to enhance material curation in engineering courses. Students pre-select materials, use NotebookLM individually and in groups to answer questions provided during the activity, and participate in a collective discussion. The evaluation process considers knowledge acquisition, source selection, and engagement. Students used different types of materials to support their answers. However, the results indicate that the quality of the responses did not significantly vary based on the type of material chosen. The key factor influencing the quality of responses was the selection of materials with greater breadth and depth of content. An improvement in response quality was observed when comparing individual and group work. This advancement can be attributed to the refinement of strategies used in task execution. However, based on the professor's perceptions, students likely did not modify the responses generated by NotebookLM. This raises a fundamental question about the role of artificial intelligence in learning: did students use AI as a support tool, or did they simply delegate the responsibility of answering to it? Therefore, to make this activity more comprehensive, it would be beneficial to implement an individual assessment to verify its effectiveness in students' understanding of technical concepts.

Keywords: NotebookLM, Artificial Intelligence, Engineering Learning.

1 Introduction

Although the discussion around the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) across various fields of knowledge has intensified recently especially since November 2022 with the emergence of large language model (LLM)-based chatbots such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Meta.ai the dissemination of AI dates to the 1950s. As the use of these technologies has advanced, so have the concerns surrounding them. In this context, some educators and researchers have dedicated themselves to understanding and applying AI as a didactic resource (McCarthy, Minsky, Rochester, & Shannon, 1955; Nguyen, Ngo, Hong, Dang, & Nguyen, 2023).

In Brazil, a study conducted in 2024 by the Brazilian Association of Higher Education Institutions (ABMES) revealed that 71% of respondents use AI regularly, with 29% using it daily and 42% weekly. In just one year, the use of AI grew from 53% to 71% (ABMES, 2024).

Given this significant increase, it becomes essential to promote AI literacy among students, enabling them to understand and critically engage with these tools. A recent study showed that students felt more comfortable using AI after learning to understand and critically analyze its applications. The pedagogical approach involved collaborative practices using digital technologies, along with discussions, project creation, and presentations. Another teaching strategy described in the literature employed simulation-based learning. In this case, students explored different AI tools and systems (such as educational chatbots, virtual assistants, and virtual

reality simulations), which enhanced their understanding of real-life situations through immersive and interactive environments (Labrague, AL Sabei, & AL Yahyaei, 2025).

An AI tool with the potential to revolutionize education is NotebookLM, developed by Google. It adopts a research-centered approach, allowing users to efficiently organize, analyze, and synthesize information all within a practical and intuitive notebook-style interface (Google, 2025). Unlike the more popular AI tools such as ChatGPT and Gemini, NotebookLM does not function as a chatbot. Instead, it operates as a specialized tool for organizing documents and various sources, effectively acting as a virtual assistant for research and writing (Nieminen, 2024).

NotebookLM is a system that combines an advanced Large Language Model (LLM), capable of accurately understanding and generating text, with the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) technique. RAG enhances the LLM's responses by incorporating information extracted from an external database in this case, documents provided by the user. This allows NotebookLM to deliver accurate and personalized answers, reducing hallucinations and enabling source tracking, making it an ideal tool for education, research, and reliable data analysis (Tozuka et al., 2024).

To use NotebookLM, users must first upload the documents and research materials they wish to analyse. The platform supports various formats, including PDFs, text files (.txt), Google Docs, web links, copied text, and YouTube video transcripts. After the upload, NotebookLM identifies key information, highlights main themes, and establishes connections between different parts of the content. Based on this analysis, it generates a concise summary and offers various content formats, such as question lists, study guides, schedules, podcasts, and chat-based interaction (Huffman & Hutson, 2024).

NotebookLM has been used in education, benefiting both teachers and students in multiple ways. It assists in generating educational materials, significantly reducing the time needed for lesson preparation (Huffman & Hutson, 2024); enables the creation of conversational-style podcasts, allowing educators without technical expertise to edit high-quality audio an effective alternative for students who prefer auditory over textual content (Huffman & Hutson, 2024; Yeo, Moorhouse, & Wan, 2025); and facilitates research comprehension by helping students make connections, synthesize information, and gain insights from multiple sources, in addition to organizing content for research-based projects (Nieminen, 2024).

While several studies have focused on the use of AI-based chatbots, little has been discussed about the application of other tools such as NotebookLM. Therefore, this paper aims to explore the use of this technology in didactic practices within Engineering courses at a Brazilian university.

2 Methodology

This research adopts a descriptive and exploratory approach, focusing on the analysis of the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a pedagogical tool in the teaching of concepts from the courses Thermoplastics Processing, Ceramic Materials Processing, and Applied Electricity. The study was conducted at the School of Industrial and Metallurgical Engineering of Volta Redonda (EIMVR). The activity was divided into different stages to ensure active and collaborative learning, as shown in Figure 1.

STEPS OF THE ACTIVITY USING NOTEBOOK LM

Figure 1. Stages of the activity using NotebookLM

2.1 Preparation for Activity

Students were instructed to conduct preliminary research on the topics covered in each course prior to the classes and were also informed about the learning objectives to be achieved. In the Applied Electricity course, students studied transformers, including their definition, types, components, operation, and applications. In the Thermoplastics Processing course, they explored FDM 3D printing, analysing its working principles and how printing parameters and material properties affect the final product. In the Ceramic Materials Processing course, students learned about the main ceramic forming methods, the effects of processing parameters on material properties, and the technical and environmental challenges of the sector.

Across all courses, students developed common skills such as curating research materials and critically analysing content generated by AI, in addition to adopting attitudes such as collaborative negotiation and individual responsibility. This approach fostered a comprehensive technical education that integrates specific knowledge with analytical skills and essential professional behaviours.

The selected supporting materials had to be uploaded to an online storage platform, with a limit of up to five items. These materials could include scientific articles, videos, podcasts, and relevant links. The main objective of this activity was to promote students' autonomy in curating reliable and relevant sources to support the proposed task.

2.2 Classroom Stage

Initially, students were introduced to the NotebookLM tool, and the guidelines for using artificial intelligence in the activity were discussed. Each student then individually answered the questions, using NotebookLM along with the supporting materials they had prepared. After this stage, students were organized into groups and collaboratively selected up to five support materials to be used with the AI tool. Together, they constructed a new, joint response, justifying their choice of sources. All materials produced, both individually and in groups, were submitted to the instructor. Finally, a discussion was held about the quality of the content generated by the AI, addressing areas for improvement and highlighting the importance of critically analysing the information provided. Students also completed a questionnaire about their participation, the method used, the skills and competencies developed and had the opportunity to leave suggestions for future activities.

2.3 Assessment

To grade students, assessments were based on specific criteria such as clarity, objectivity, and the relevance of the points addressed in relation to the topic. Grades ranged from 1 to 10, ensuring a precise and consistent evaluation. In assessing curatorial ability, the types, content, and languages of the support materials selected by the students were analyzed and compared to their grades to determine whether there was a relationship between the quality of their responses and the material chosen. A quantitative analysis was also conducted comparing the grades of individual work with those of group work. The questionnaire responses and the discussions held with students enabled an evaluation of the advantages and disadvantages of the applied methodology.

2.4 Professors' and Students' perceptions

The professors' perception was recorded through direct observation of the activity's development in the classroom, with notes on student engagement, interaction, and participation. Additionally, students were required to submit a written document containing the references used, the justification for their choice, and the resolution of the proposed task, which also contributed to the analysis of the effectiveness of the adopted approach. Complementing this perspective, students' perception of the methodology adopted in the activity was assessed through an online questionnaire created using Google Forms. The students answered questions about their experience with the classroom dynamics, enabling a qualitative and quantitative analysis of their collective impressions.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Professors' Perception

This study presents professor's perceptions regarding the curated materials used by students during the first stage of the activity, described as the individual task.

In the Thermoplastics Processing course, analysis of student performance revealed that those who scored highest (9.0 points) on the individual assessment demonstrated a diversified approach to information seeking. These students consulted different types of sources, including national and international articles, dissertations, theses, videos, websites, undergraduate theses, conference proceedings, and presentations. Although it was not possible to identify a specific type of material as decisive for better performance, the strategic selection of sources based on their breadth and depth was a distinguishing factor. Nevertheless, the overall average score for the individual activity was 8.5 points, indicating satisfactory performance by the class as a whole.

In the Ceramic Materials Processing course, a clear correlation was observed between the quality of the selected sources and the students' individual performance. The student who earned the highest score (9.0 points) used a 2020 review article, a 1990 book chapter regarded as a reference in the field, and other recent scientific papers. In contrast, a student who scored lower (7.0 points) cited older references, published between 2000 and 2007, along with an undergraduate research report and classroom support material. This suggests that selecting more in-depth and up-to-date materials significantly contributed to better academic performance.

In the Applied Electricity course, students who scored the highest on the individual assessment primarily relied on national articles, undergraduate theses, dissertations, and lecture notes. Notably, approximately 20 students used national articles, 25 referred to lecture notes, and 23 accessed theses or dissertations. This pattern indicates that sources offering a state-of-the-art overview tend to have a more developed theoretical

framework, which facilitates a better understanding of the topic and leads to higher evaluation scores. The average score for the individual activity was 8.0 points.

The findings show that the quality, diversity, and recency of sources played a fundamental role in students' performance on individual assessments. In all three courses, a common pattern emerged: students who sought more in-depth information such as scientific articles, book chapters, theses, and final papers achieved better results. The combined analysis of the three experiences reveals that strategic source selection, along with the ability to analyse and synthesize researched content, was crucial to success in the individual stage.

In the group activity stage, students' average scores improved, though the extent varied across courses. In the first case Thermoplastics Processing there was a modest 2% increase in the final average, raising it to 8.7 points. This gain was attributed to more efficient task strategies. Groups, already aware of the questions, selected more targeted materials, reducing redundancy and improving content comprehension.

In the Ceramic Materials Processing course, scores showed a more substantial increase of approximately 10%. This improvement was linked to the careful selection of references, with many groups relying on materials previously selected by the highest-performing individual student. Thus, sharing high-quality sources within the groups directly contributed to overall performance gains.

In the Applied Electricity course, the average increase was 5%, with final averages reaching 8.5 points. This improvement was associated with the greater opportunity for collaborative discussion on known questions and strategic material curation.

Overall, all three courses saw improved student performance in the group stage, driven by more deliberate source selection and the use of materials previously chosen by high-performing students in the individual phase.

Finally, the use of NotebookLM as an educational tool generated varying perceptions among professors, particularly regarding student autonomy in knowledge construction. Although all professors noted that students made few modifications to AI-generated responses, interpretations of this phenomenon differed, raising questions about the methodology's effectiveness in fostering meaningful learning.

A common observation among professors was that, in both individual and group activities, students tended to input information into the AI and accept the generated responses with minimal alteration. This raises concerns about the role of AI in the learning process: were students using NotebookLM as a complementary resource, or were they delegating the responsibility of knowledge construction entirely to the tool? This is a central question when assessing the methodology's true effectiveness. Nonetheless, this also highlights a broader concern regarding AI use in education. To achieve truly promising results, it is essential that students are guided in the appropriate use of such tools, developing their critical thinking skills when evaluating AI-generated responses. As (Bozkurt, et al., 2024) point out, AI in education should be linked to the promotion of critical thinking so that technology serves as a support rather than a substitute in the learning process.

Professors proposed several hypotheses to explain the lack of student authorship in their responses. Some suggested that students trusted the quality of their sources and assumed the AI's answers were correct and required no revision. Others noted that limited technical knowledge may have hindered students' ability to critically assess the generated content. Additionally, there may have been a communication gap, with students misunderstanding that the AI was meant to be a support tool rather than the primary source of their responses. These hypotheses align with the findings of (Modran, Chamunorwa, & Ursutiu, 2023 e Costa, Hirayama, & Santos, 2023), who emphasize that AI-generated responses should not be treated as definitive, but rather as supplemental information to support the learning process.

Despite these limitations, one positive aspect emerged: group responses showed slight improvement. This can be attributed to the fact that discussions among students encouraged a deeper reading of the selected materials, fostering more critical engagement. However, the lack of substantial modifications in the responses still suggests that the use of NotebookLM needs to be enhanced to ensure greater student involvement in the learning process. Thus, while NotebookLM shows potential as a didactic tool, its implementation requires refinement to ensure that students not only develop the ability to search for information but also the skills to analyse, question, and reframe it critically and autonomously.

3.2 Students' Perception

Based on the responses provided by the students, the effectiveness of the teaching method using NotebookLM was assessed in terms of participation, method efficiency, competencies, reflections, and suggestions. Regarding student participation, more than 80% adherence was observed in the courses analyzed. As for the effectiveness of the teaching method, the students who recognized the tool as beneficial for learning were the same ones who reported active participation in the activity. In the class with lower engagement, the perceived effectiveness of the method was also reduced. These data indicate a strong relationship between student participation and their perception of their own learning.

Although some authors suggest that behavioural participation may not have a direct influence on learning perception (Navarro, Vega, Bayona, Bernal, & Garcia, 2024), others have shown that different forms of engagement including interaction with AI and collaborative activities can influence how students perceive their learning process and the development of competencies (Tzirides et al., 2024; Labrague, AL Sabei, & AL Yahyaei, 2025), which is believed to have occurred in the context of these studies.

When considering the three dimensions of engagement: cognitive, emotional, and behavioural, it was found that students with higher cognitive involvement also demonstrated a deeper perception of learning, as they showed a strong intention to learn. Similarly, high levels of learning were observed among students who were emotionally connected to the activity. Another relevant factor is behavioural engagement, as students willing to put effort into completing activities tend to achieve more positive results (Navarro, Vega, Bayona, Bernal, & Garcia, 2024).

When analysing the competencies perceived by students, teamwork stood out, identified by more than 80% of participants.

Understanding and problem-solving were mentioned by more than 60% of students. These competencies had already been discussed by other authors, and their development is fundamental as it allows students to learn from each other, share different perspectives, and build knowledge collaboratively (Labrague, AL Sabei, & AL Yahyaei, 2025).

Competencies such as proactivity, entrepreneurship, and innovation were mentioned exclusively by students of Applied Electricity and Ceramic Materials Processing, while leadership was identified only by students in the Applied Electricity course.

In addition to the competencies initially evaluated, students also highlighted skills not suggested by the professors in the survey, such as the use of new technologies with emphasis on artificial intelligence (AI) highlighting an emerging demand for knowledge related to digital tools in academic and professional contexts. Some authors emphasize that competence in the use of AI has become increasingly significant in various professional settings, as developing this competence prepares students for their future careers (Labrague, AL Sabei, & AL Yahyaei, 2025).

Although some students initially had a negative perception of using AI as a support tool, many came to recognize it as an important resource in the teaching-learning process, when used appropriately. Some statements also show how the activity sparked curiosity and engagement with the topic, as in the following comments: "I was surprised to discover that there is an AI for which I create the database," and "I thought using Google involved reading articles, but it turned out to be a lesson about the NotebookLM AI."

There is clear evidence of appreciation for the development of digital competencies, as revealed in the following statement: "The information about the AI tool made me curious about how important it is to select the right sources, and that led me to reconsider the articles I chose."

This type of reflection highlights progress in critical thinking, as students recognize the importance of source quality.

Although the professors expected the use of the tool to promote an even deeper level of reflection, it is undeniable that there were, in fact, signs of critical thinking among the students. However, the development of this analytical posture still needs to be encouraged in a more structured way in order to enhance student agency in the use of digital technologies.

4 Conclusion

This study investigated the use of NotebookLM in instructional practices within engineering courses at a Brazilian university. The findings reveal that students did not engage with artificial intelligence merely as a support tool. In practice, most students tended to adopt the AI-generated responses with minimal modifications. The instructional design anticipated that AI would serve as a starting point to foster critical thinking and autonomous knowledge construction. Students were expected to critically analyze, question, and reformulate the content provided by the tool based on their own reasoning. However, the results suggest that this more reflective and critical engagement with AI still requires further encouragement and development among the participants.

The outcomes of the activity raise an important question: did students genuinely learn during the process? With regard to the technical content addressed through AI, the design of the activity did not yield concrete evidence of deep learning. In most cases, the responses submitted by students were direct reproductions of AI outputs, lacking elaboration or conceptual depth. Classroom discussions were limited to reading the generated responses, with little indication of independent argumentation or critical understanding. From the professors' perspective, there were no clear signs of sustained assimilation of content throughout the course following the activity.

Nevertheless, it would be inaccurate to conclude that students acquired no learning during the process. On the contrary, they demonstrated meaningful progress in their interaction with artificial intelligence. Students exhibited increased engagement with the tool, exploring its functionalities, questioning its mechanisms, uploading various file types, and collaborating in curating the input materials for the AI. These behaviours reflect the development of skills in the psychomotor and affective domains, particularly in terms of technological proficiency and collaborative learning. Thus, while cognitive gains related to conceptual content may have been limited, the activity contributed to other significant dimensions of the educational process.

In the specific case of NotebookLM which generates responses exclusively from user-provided material students expressed greater confidence in the outputs, as the reference material had been selected by themselves. This appeared to reduce concerns about incorrect answers and fostered a stronger sense of reliability and trust in the generated information. Students felt more comfortable engaging with the tool, given

the assurance that the AI would not "hallucinate" or produce information disconnected from the curated knowledge base.

It is essential to emphasize, however, that artificial intelligence must be understood as a resource to support critical analysis, rather than a source of ready-made or definitive answers. Its integration into educational settings should serve to stimulate inquiry, critical reflection, and the construction of knowledge, not to substitute these core learning processes.

Based on these reflections, the instructional team proposes methodological adjustments aimed at reinforcing students' active participation. One potential strategy is the implementation of individual assessments following the activity to verify assimilation of technical concepts. Furthermore, it is imperative to promote artificial intelligence literacy, enabling students to adopt a critical stance toward technological tools and to recognize that, regardless of the resource employed, the learning process must remain student-centered and inquiry-driven.

Finally, the study contributes to the discussion on artificial intelligence literacy as a transversal competency required in engineering, reinforcing the idea that future engineers must be prepared not only to use AI, but also to understand it, critically evaluate it, and integrate it ethically and responsibly into their professional practice.

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